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Design, synthesis of bisbenzimidazole dithiol derivatives and analogs

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Abstract

The benzimidazole scaffold is an important pharmacophore and one of the preferred structures in medicinal chemistry due to the wide range of biological activities of its derivatives. Here in this article, the synthesis of two series of compounds, namely bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane derivatives and analogs (4a-e) and bis(benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol derivatives and analogs (5a-e) are described. These compounds were synthesized by first designing 2-mercaptobenzimidazole derivatives and analogs (2a-e) by action of orthophenylenediamine and analogs (1a-e) with carbon disulfide. Reaction of thiols (2a-e) with diiodomethane leads to bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane derivatives and analogs (4a-e). Their treatment in glacial acetic acid led to their oxidation to bis(benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol derivatives and analogs (5a-e). The structures of the synthesized compounds were characterized by ¹H, ¹³C Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) analyses.

Keywords: Benzimidazole; Dithiol; Oxidation; Diiodomethane; Analogs

1. Introduction

The benzimidazole scaffold is an important pharmacophore and a preferred structure in medicinal chemistry due to the wide range of biological activities of its derivatives. These compounds have shown several biological activities namely antioxidant [1,2], antimicrobial [3,8], antiviral including anti-HIV [9,11], anti-inflammatory [12,15] and anticancer [16,20]. Derivatives of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole, the most important benzimidazole derivatives, show a wide range of interesting biological activities including anti-HIV [21], antiprotozoal [22], antitumor [23] and antimicrobial [23,24]. This entity was used for the synthesis of a variety of bioactive compounds, some of which are used clinically with proven efficacy. The commonly used anti-ulcer drugs was derived from 2-mercaptobenzimidazole. These include omeprazole, lansoprazole, rabeprazole, ilaprazole and esomeprazole which inhibit the secretion of stomach acid. Considering the importance of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole derivatives, this work is focused on the design of new bis(benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol derivatives and analogs.

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2. Material and methods

The solvents and reagents are of high quality and come from Aldrich Chemical or Fischer Scientific (France). The reactions were followed by TLC on pre-coated Merck 60 F254 silica gel plates and revealed using a UV lamp (6 W, 254 nm, and/or 365 nm). The purification of the products was carried out on a Merck G60 silica gel column. Melting points (m.p °C) were determined using a temperature gradient (40-265 °C) Kofler bench.

For all compounds, the Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra of ^1H and ^{13}C were recorded on a Bruker 300 advance device with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO- d_6) as the solvent, while tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as an internal standard for chemical displacements (δ) expressed in ppm. The NMR spectra description use the following symbols: s (singlet), d (doublet), dd (double doublet), t (triplet), q (quadruplet), m (multiplet), br (broad). The mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL JMS DX300 spectrometer in ESI mode (electrospray/quadrupolar ionization or ESI mass).

2.1. General method for synthesis of thiols 2a-e

To a solution of orthophenylenediamine derivatives (1 eq, 46.3 mmol) in 15 mL of dimethylformamide (DMF) cooled in an ice bath, carbon disulfide (5 eq, 231.2 mmol) was added dropwise. After 24 to 48 hours of stirring at room temperature, 200 mL of water were added to the reaction mixture. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed several times with water and dried in an oven (80 °C). The crude was recrystallized in a water/ethanol mixture (50/50).

2.1.1. 2-mercaptobenzimidazole 2a

Reaction time: 24 h, beige crystals, yield = 82%, m.p > 265 °C. ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 12.54 (s, 1H, NH), 7.16-7.01 (m, 4H, H_{Ar}), 3.37 (s, 1H, SH). ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 167.23, 131.36, 121.44, 108.59. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₇H₇N₂S (M + H⁺) = 151.025 Found = 151.028.

2.1.2. 5-methyl-2-mercapto-1H-benzimidazole 2b

Reaction time: 24 h, brown crystals, yield = 84%, m.p > 265 °C. NMR ^1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 12.51 (s, 1H, NH), 7.23-7.12 (m, 3H, H_{Ar}), 3.23 (s, 1H, SH), 2.36 (s, 3H, CH₃). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 147.11, 131.79, 128.02, 123.43, 109.38, 107.64, 20.02. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₈H₉N₂S (M+H⁺) = 165.041 Found = 165.041.

2.1.3. 5-nitro-2-mercapto-1H-benzimidazole 2c

Reaction time: 48 h, orange crystals, yield = 92%, m.p = 262-264 °C. NMR ^1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 12.54 (s, 1H, NH), 8.30-7.50 (m, 4H, H_{Ar}), 2.50 (s, 1H, SH). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 171.49, 142.48, 137.29, 132.15, 118.82, 109.11, 104.56. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₇H₆N₃O₂S (M+H⁺) = 196.010 Found = 196.013.

2.1.4. 2-mercaptobenzothiazole 2d

Reaction time: 24 h, beige crystals, yield = 99%, m.p = 180-182 °C. NMR ^1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.25-7.70 (m, 4H, H_{Ar}), 3.39 (br s, 1H, SH). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 141.20, 129.30, 127.09, 124.14, 121.70, 112.38. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₇H₆NS₂ (M+H⁺) = 167.986 Found = 167.989.

2.1.5. 6-methyl-2-mercaptobenzoxazole 2e

Reaction time: 24 h, beige crystals, yield = 77%, m.p = 210-212 °C. NMR ^1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.10-7.32 (m, 3H, H_{Ar}), 3.30 (br s, 1H, SH), 2.36 (s, 3H, CH₃). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 148.33, 133.65, 128.84, 125.66, 110.19, 109.93, 20.86. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₈H₈NOS (M+H⁺) = 166.025 Found = 166.027.

2.2. General method for synthesis of bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane derivatives and analogs 3a-b, 4a-e

To compounds 2a-e (1 eq, 6.7 mmol) suspended in 10 mL of anhydrous ethanol, diiodomethane (1.2 eq, 8.04 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed with ethanol from 4 hours to 24 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was neutralized with sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (10%) and extracted with dichloromethane (3 x 50 mL). The organic layer was washed with water, dried over magnesium sulfate and the solvent was removed under *vacuo*. The crude obtained was purified by silica gel column chromatography.

2.2.1. 2-iodothiomethyl-1H-benzimidazole 3a

Reaction time = 4h, orange crystals, yield = 14%, m.p = 208-210 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 12.77 (s, 1H, NH), 7.23-7.69 (m, 4H, H_{Ar}), 5.69 (s, 2H, CH₂). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 168.96, 136.82, 131.10, 124.06, 122.37, 110.67, 109.65, 36.12. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₈H₉N₂SI (M+H⁺) = 290.937 Found = 289.939.

2.2.2. Bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane 4a

Reaction time = 4h, beige crystals, yield = 74%, m.p = 224-226 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 7.2-7.67 (m, 8H, H_{Ar}), 5.71 (s, 2H, CH₂). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm) : 158.2, 131.55, 123.89, 123.67, 123.48, 123.16, 122.79, 114.62, 114.26, 110.91, 110.60, 39.36. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄N₄S₂ (M+H⁺) = 313.050 Found = 313.053.

2.2.3. 2-iodothiomethyl-5-methyl-1H-benzimidazole 3b

Reaction time = 4h, brown crystals, yield = 11%, m.p = 230-232 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.67-8.33 (m, 3H, H_{Ar}), 5.33 (s, 2H, ICH₂), 2.5 (s, 3H, CH₃). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 154.76 (C=N), 140.24, 129.72, 118.19, 113.70, 110.71, 110.61, 38.90, 34.70. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₉H₁₀N₂SI (M+H⁺) = 304.953 Found = 304.956.

2.2.4. Bis(5-thiomethylbenzimidazol-2-yl)-methane 4b

Reaction time = 4h, brown crystals, yield = 68%, m.p = 244-246 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.02-7.38 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 5.31 (d, 2H, CH₂), 2.54 and 2.38 (2s, 6H, 2 CH₃). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 149.3, 135.91, 131.64, 131.54, 123.65, 123.47, 113.88, 113.41, 117.54, 117.31, 110.20, 109.84, 36.12, 21.39 and 21.23. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₇H₁₇N₄S₂ (M+H⁺) = 341.082 Found = 341.080.

2.2.5. Bis(5-nitro-thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane 4c

Reaction time: 8h, yellow crystals, yield = 72%, m.p > 265 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 12.69 (s, 2H, NH), 7.03-7.51 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 5.69 (s, 2H, CH₂). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 169.23, 147.83, 147.25, 134.83, 134.32, 131.28, 130.97, 123.89, 123.62, 113.39, 113.21, 110.10, 109.80, 37.05. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₅H₁₁N₆O₄S₂ (M+H⁺) = 403.020 Found = 403.023.

2.2.6. Bis(thiobenzothiazol-2-yl)methane 4d

Reaction time: 24h, orange crystals, yield = 82%, m.p = 223-225 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.15-7.62 (m, 8H, H_{Ar}), 4.31 (s, 2H, CH₂). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 169.97, 136.30, 126.66, 126.38, 123.26, 123.06, 122.67, 122.56, 111.72, 111.45, 33.91. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₅H₁₁N₂S₄ (M+H⁺) = 346.973 Found = 343.975.

2.2.7. Bis(6-methylthiobenzothiazol-2-yl)methane 4e

Reaction time: 24 h, red crystals, yield = 78%, m.p = 252-254 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 6.95-7.10 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 3.36 (s, 2H, CH₂), 2.33 (s, 6 H, 2 CH₃). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 154.56, 143.49, 131.35, 127.87, 127.71, 124.04, 110.27, 110.00, 109.33, 20.91. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₇H₁₅N₂O₂S₂ (M+H⁺) = 343.050 Found = 343.053.

2.3. General method for synthesis of bisbenzimidazole dithiols and analogs 5a-e

To compounds 2a-e (1 eq, 10 mmol) suspended in 20 mL of glacial acetic acid, were added few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 minutes. Then it was allowed to reflux on acetic acid for 4 to 7 hours. After cooling, the mixture was neutralized with a concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution. The precipitate formed was filtered, wrung out, washed several times with water and dried in an oven (70°C). The crude obtained was recrystallised with ethanol.

2.3.1. 1,2-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol 5a

Reaction time: 4 h, beige foam, yield = 68%, m.p > 265 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 13.11 (s, 1H, NH), 7.28-7.72 (m, 8H, H_{Ar}). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 168.55, 142.32, 140.84, 132.90, 132.10, 131.24, 124.58, 123.27, 123.05, 122.08, 118.90, 112.26, 110.10. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for C₁₄H₁₁N₄S₂ (M+H⁺) = 298.035 Found = 298.037.

2.3.2. 1,2-(5-methyl-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol 5b

Reaction time: 4 h, brown crystals, yield = 75%, m.p = 238-240 °C. NMR ¹H (DMSO-*d*₆, 300 MHz) δ (ppm): δ (ppm): 12.39 (s, 2H, 2 NH), 7.39-7.56 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 2.28 (s, 2H, 2 CH₃). NMR ¹³C (DMSO-*d*₆, 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 167.76, 132.46, 131.64,

130.20, 129.81, 129.33, 127.41, 123.18, 120.87, 109.60, 109.10, 108.98, 108.14, 21.06 and 20.93. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for $C_{16}H_{15}N_2S_2$ ($M+H^+$) = 326.066 Found = 326.068.

2.3.3. 1,2-(5-nitro-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol 5c

Reaction time: 7h, yellow crystals, yield = 71% (706 mg, 1.82 mmol) m.p > 265 °C. NMR 1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.10-7.94 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 11.39 and 11.14 (2s, 2H, 2 NH). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm) : 155.56, 146.67, 142.22, 136.11, 118.89, 107.78, 103.88. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_2O_4S_2$ ($M+H^+$) = 388.005 Found = 388.008.

2.3.4. 1,2-(benzothiazol-2-yl)dithiol 5d

Reaction time : 4h, beige crystals, yield = 87%, m.p > 265 °C. NMR 1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.09-7.29 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 2.41 (s, 6H, 2 CH_3). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 170.02, 141.25, 136.32, 126.85, 126.39, 123.92, 123.51, 122.83, 122.57, 112.43, 112.09. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_2S_4$ ($M+H^+$) = 331.957 Found = 331.959.

2.3.5. 1,2-(6-methylbenzoxazol-2-yl)dithiol 5e

Reaction time: 24 h, beige crystals, yield = 76% (755 mg, 2.30 mmol), m.p = 128-130 °C. NMR 1H (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm): 7.09-7.29 (m, 6H, H_{Ar}), 2.41 (s, 6H, 2 CH_3). NMR ^{13}C (DMSO- d_6 , 75 MHz) δ (ppm): 179.89, 148.37, 133.69, 133.39, 128.86, 125.70, 125.96, 125.40, 110.23, 109.97, 109.60, 21.13 and 20.92. HRMS (ESI) Calc. for $C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_2S_2$ ($M+H^+$) = 328.034 Found = 328.036.

3. Results and discussion

Bis(benzimidazol-2-yl)dithiol and their analogs 4a-e and 5a-e were synthesized by first preparing 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and its analogs 2a-e. It was done by the Van Allan method [25]. This consisted on a condensation reaction between orthophenylenediamine derivatives and analogs (1a-e) with carbon disulfide in dimethylformamide (DMF). The yields of compounds 2a-e were obtained in range of 82 to 99%. The 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and its analogs 2a-e react with diiodomethane and lead to the bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane derivatives and analogs 3a-e. This reaction involves the formation of a monosubstituted iodomethylene compound that undergoes a cross or duplication reaction in the presence of another thiol. In the case of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and its 5-methyl derivative, monosubstituted compound can be isolated in low yield. Bisbenzimidazole dithiols and analogs 5a-e were obtained by oxidation of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and analogs 2a-e in glacial acetic acid in the presence of catalytic amount of concentrated sulfuric acid (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Synthesis of Bisbenzimidazole dithiols and analogs

The structure of the different compounds was confirmed by 1H , ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, and HRMS analyses. Indeed, on the 1H NMR spectra of the various compounds, there are no distinct peaks for the SH group protons between 2.50 and 3.20 ppm characteristic, and there is an increase in signals in the aromatic region which clearly indicates compounds duplication. This can also be seen in the ^{13}C NMR spectra. Particularly for bis(thiobenzimidazol-2-yl)methane and analogs 4a-e, the presence of a methylene group between the two sulfur atoms is characterized in 1H NMR by the singlet between 4.30 and 5.80 ppm and in ^{13}C NMR by the peak between 33.90 and 39.40 ppm.

4. Conclusion

In this work, bisbenzimidazol-2-yl dithiols and analogs (4a-e and 5-e) were synthesized from the previously obtained precursors, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and 2a-e analogs. The yields of all compounds were greater than 50% and their structures were confirmed by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectroscopic analyzes. In the case of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole and its 5-methyl derivatives, monosubstituted compound can be obtained during the reaction with diiodomethane. An ongoing study of their anthelmintic activities is currently underway with the collaboration of biologists and the first results are promising.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Author contributions

K. Y. G. M. performed the syntheses, T.E.C participated in the purification of the compounds and write the paper. A. T. and S.C. participated in the spectroscopic analyses. A. F. K. , S.C and D.S. designed and conducted the project. All authors have read and agreed on the published version of the manuscript.

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